

HIGH-PRESSURE RTM PROCESS VARIANTS FOR MANUFACTURING OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

The transport sector in its current status is one of the largest sources for greenhouse gas emissions. The European Commission has proposed to set a CO₂ emission limit on vehicle manufacturers for new automobiles registered in the European Union in order to reduce the CO₂ emissions from running automobiles. If this is exceeded, the concerned manufacturer will be liable for financial penalties. The research on different materials indicate that the potential of automotive body light-weighting can reach 7 % after structure optimization, high strength steel use can allow further weight reduction, full aluminum body can lead to 30-50 % weight reduction and using continuous fiber reinforced composites further weight reduction can be achieved [1, 2]. The continuous fiber reinforced composites can be manufactured by either injection process in which the textile reinforcement is impregnated by using suitable resin during component manufacturing or by prepreg process in which the reinforcements are pre-impregnated prior to component manufacturing. The resin transfer molding process (RTM), one of the injection processes, has been considered and evaluated for manufacturing structural automotive components based on continuous fiber reinforced composites [3]. However the RTM process in its current status is still limited to low-volume manufacturing capacity and number of parts per year < 25000 per production setup is generally achieved in the RTM process [11]. In classical RTM process the dry three-dimensional preform is placed into the mold cavity and resin-hardener mixture is injected at low pressure of 1 to 20 bar into the closed mold [4]. The low flow rate of

resin and low injection pressure in the classical RTM process results in longer resin injection time. This limits the use of fast cure resins in the RTM process. In order to adapt the RTM process for high volume manufacturing, it is essential to develop new process strategies that allow reduction of the process cycle time. Newly developed state of the art high-pressure RTM equipment technology allow injection of resin under high flow rate in the mold cavity. The combination of high-pressure pumps for dosing resin and hardener, and self-cleaning mixing head of such equipment guarantees precise resin and hardener mixing along with materials injection into the mold at constant defined flow rate (20-200 g/s) though high flow resistance is created in the mold cavity [5, 6]. Using HP-RTM process equipment two different variants, namely high-pressure injection RTM (HP-IRTM) and high-pressure compression RTM (HP-CRTM), can be implemented for the manufacturing of continuous-fiber reinforced composites which are discussed in detail below.

HP-IRTM process

The HP-IRTM process differs from the classical RTM process only in terms of the processing equipment for the resin system. The resin injection sequence in HP-IRTM process is shown in figure 1. In the classical RTM process, low pressure mixing and dosing equipment is used for processing resins, whereas in the HP-IRTM process resin mixing and dosing is carried out using high-pressure RTM equipment. Similar to the classical RTM process, in the HP-IRTM process the preform is placed into the mold cavity and then the mold is completely closed to compact the preform to final part thickness. Once

the mold is closed, the resin and hardener mixture is injected into the cavity under high injection speed. The high throughput rate allows the cavity to fill quickly, significantly reducing the resin injection time. As the resin can be injected into the cavity in a shorter time, this process variant allows the use of resins with relatively high reactivity. After the resin curing reaction is completed the part can be demolded [5, 6, 9].

Fig. 1. Resin injection sequence in the HP-IRTM process

HP-CRTM process

Fig. 2. Resin injection sequence in the HP-CRTM process

As can be seen in figure 2 the HP-CRTM process is a combination of resin transfer molding (RTM) and compression molding in which, similar to the HP-IRTM process, high-pressure RTM equipment is used for processing of resins. If conducted without the use of high pressure RTM equipment, the process is referred to in the literature as the Compression RTM (CRTM) process. In this process, the preform is placed into the mold cavity and then the mold is closed partially, leaving a small gap between the upper mold surface and the fiber preform. The resin is introduced into the gap, flows easily over the preform and may partially impregnate it. Once the required amount of resin has been injected into the gap and the injection point is closed, the mold closes further and applies high compression pressure to squeeze the resin into the preform, especially in the z-direction. In this step, the preform is compacted to achieve the desired part thickness and fiber volume fraction. The part can be demolded after the resin has cured. The quick resin injection and fast impregnation by applying compression force allows HP-CRTM process to be used for highly reactive resins thereby allowing faster manufacturing of the high-performance composites [7-9].

In the current paper both the HP-RTM process variants were characterized for manufacturing carbon fiber reinforced composites. The resin injection speed was varied for both the process variants to evaluate the high-volume manufacturing aspect of the HP-RTM process technology. Additionally, the effect of vacuum application on the mechanical properties of the manufactured laminates was investigated.

2 Materials

For the current HP-RTM process studies, an epoxy resin system from Dow Automotive Systems was used. A carbon-fiber-based biaxial non-crimp fabric, commercially available as Panex 35, based on 50K roving from Zoltek was used as a reinforcement material for studying the HP-RTM process variants. The used non-crimp fabric had a surface area weight of 300 g/m².

3 Process equipment

A plate mold specially designed and constructed for studying HP-RTM process variants was used to

compare the HP-IRTM process with HP-CRTM process.

1. Cavity (910 mm x 560 mm)
2. Vulkollan® gasket in the lower mold half for clamping fibers
3. Metallic surface in the upper mold half for clamping fibers
4. Vulkollan® gasket in the mold parting line
5. Injection gate (point geometry)
6. Conical shaped injection runner
7. Adapter plate for mounting mixing head

Fig. 3. HP-RTM mold concept

Figure 3 shows the conceptual sketch of this metallic plate mold. The cavity of this mold measured 910 mm x 560 mm and the cavity height varied between 1.55 mm to 1.75 mm near and away from the injection point respectively if the mold was completely closed. The injection gate of film geometry was designed in the middle of the lower mold half. This mold facilitated vacuum application through vacuum ports which were located on either side of the upper mold half. Four pressure sensors were situated in the lower mold half at different positions. Sensors S1 and S2 were located symmetrically to each other at a distance of 180 mm from the injection point (hereafter referred as sensors near injection point) and sensors S3 and S4 were located symmetrically to each other at a distance of 410 mm from the injection point (hereafter referred as sensors away from the injection point).

A hydraulic compression press from the company Dieffenbacher GmbH (press type - DYL630/500) was used to mount the RTM mold as well as to precisely apply defined compression force and to

control the mold gap and gap closure speed during the HP-CRTM process study. The maximum force capacity of such a press is 5000 kN with active parallel control during mold closure. For the mixing of the chosen epoxy resin and curing agent, and for injecting the reactive resin into the mold cavity, HP RTM equipment from the company KraussMaffei Technologies GmbH was used.

4 Process parameter matrix

Table 1 summarizes the process parameters used for studying the HP-RTM process variants. A laminate layup based on 5 layers of selected carbon fabric [0/90#/+45/-45#0/90#-45/+45#90/0] was used for manufacturing the laminates using chosen process parameters. For manufacturing laminates, 650 g of resin was injected into the cavity for all the selected experimental series. This resin amount is slightly higher than the theoretically calculated resin amount required for impregnating laminates of size 910 x 560 x 1.9 mm size. The thickness of 1.9 mm was considered with a goal to achieve approximately 48-50% fiber volume content in the laminates. The epoxy resin was preheated to 80°C and amine hardener was processed at room temperature in the high-pressure RTM equipment. A mixing head pressure of approximately 120 bar was set for resin and hardener to guarantee homogeneous materials mixing.

Experimental series	Process	Resin injection rate [g/s]	Resin injection time [s]	Mold gap [mm]	Gap closure speed [mm/s]
1	HP-IRTM	40	16.3	-	-
2	HP-IRTM	60	10.8	-	-
3	HP-IRTM	80	8.1	-	-
4	HP-CRTM	40	16.3	0.3	0.2
5	HP-CRTM	60	10.8	0.3	0.2
6	HP-CRTM	80	8.1	0.3	0.2

Tab. 1. Process parameters used for studying HP-RTM process variants

For investigating both the HP-RTM process variants the resin injection rate was varied in steps from 40 - 60 - 80 g/s which resulted in different resin injection time accordingly. In both the process variants a press force of 3100 kN was applied on the mold which is equivalent to 60 bar cavity pressure for the laminate size of 910 x 560 mm. As per the process characteristic, during the HP-IRTM processing of the laminates no mold gap was used and resin was injected into the completely closed mold at a press force 3100 kN. In case of HP-CRTM

process the mold was closed to 0.3 mm mold gap (press force 0 kN) and at this mold gap the resin was injected into the mold cavity. After the resin injection was completed, the mold was closed and 3100 kN press force was applied. For each experimental series, 3 laminates were manufactured with and without use of vacuum to confirm the process reproducibility. Also, for all the experimental series laminates were cured for 300 s in the mold.

5 Materials characterization

The manufactured laminates were tested using following norms:

1. DIN EN ISO 7822 for characterization of the fiber volume content
2. DIN EN ISO 14125 for characterization of the flexural properties
3. DIN EN ISO 14130 for characterization of the inter-laminar shear strength (ILSS)

For the materials characterization at least 5 samples were tested per norm to calculate the standard deviation in the samples in order to understand the influence of selected process and process parameter on the laminate quality.

6 Results and discussions

6.1 Process analysis

During laminates manufacturing by selected process variants the real-time process parameters from the injection equipment were exported and analyzed to evaluate the effect of selected process variants on the stability of the injection process and cavity pressure built-up pattern.

Figure 4 shows the summary of the process data from the injection equipment for a laminate manufactured using the HP-IRTM process and resin flow rate of 80 g/s without use of vacuum. This figure is divided into three important sections, namely press closure, resin injection and curing. The press closure step is purely a function of the selected press closure profile and it may vary in accordance with the used profile. In the HP-IRTM process the required press force is built on the mold at the end of press closure step. The typical process characteristic of HP-IRTM and HP-CRTM can be seen in the resin injection step. The resin injection step started after

31 s from the start of the process cycle step. During this process step the high-pressure mixing head of the injection equipment opened, resulting in resin and hardener mixing under high pressure, and the reactive resin mixture was injected into the cavity at a defined flow rate in 8.1 s time. As can be observed during the resin injection step the resin pressure increased to 142 bar from an initial value of 131 bar, whereas, the hardener pressure remained constant to 130 bar which is same as prior to the injection step. In addition, during this step the cavity pressure increased continuously indicating that the impregnation of fibers was carried out in the HP-IRTM process during resin injection step. As the pressure sensors were placed at a distance of 180 mm and 410 mm from the injection point, an increase in the cavity pressure was realized with a time delay of 2 s near the injection point (NIP), and 6 s away from the injection (AIP) point after the resin injection step was started. The maximum measured cavity pressure in the mold was 62 bar near the injection point and 49 bar away from the injection point. Once the required amount of resin was injected into the cavity the mixing head closed again and the resin and hardener were shifted back to re-circulation mode. After the resin injection step was completed, the curing step followed during which the laminate was cured and then the laminate was demolded. During the curing step a continuous drop in the cavity pressure was observed which is attributed to a combination of resin shrinkage and minor resin flow out of the cavity through the gaskets until the gel point of the resin system was reached. As only a drop in the cavity pressure was observed in the curing step, the complete time scale for process analysis in figure 4 is limited to 80 s only from the process start.

Fig. 4. Process parameter analysis for the HP-IRTM process at 80 g/s resin injection rate

Fig. 5. Process parameter analysis for the HP-CRTM process at 80 g/s resin injection rate

Figure 5 shows the summary of the process data for a laminate manufactured using the HP-CRTM process and resin flow rate of 80 g/s without use of vacuum. If compared to the HP-IRTM process, an additional compression step can be observed in the process data summary. In the press closure step the press was closed to a defined mold gap of 0.3 mm and in this case the press force is not yet applied on the mold. The resin injection step started after 35 s from the start of the process cycle step. During the resin injection step, the high-pressure mixing head opened, resulting in resin and hardener mixing under high pressure and resin injection at defined resin flow rate in 8.1 s in a partially open mold cavity. Unlike the HP-IRTM process, as the resin injection step started, the resin did not increase during this HP-CRTM experiment. The resin and hardener pressure during the injection step remained constant at 125 bar which is equivalent to the set pressure value before starting resin injection step. Unlike the HP-IRTM process, almost no increase of cavity pressure near or away from the injection point was observed during the whole resin injection step. It indicates that probably the fibers inside the roving's were not completely impregnated during resin injection step. After resin injection the mixing head closed and then the compression step was carried out. The press closed the partially open mold completely, applying the defined compression force of 3100 kN. During the compression step, which lasted for 2-3 s, there was an immediate increase in

the cavity pressure which indicates that the resin was squeezed in the fibers thereby leading to their impregnation by the resin. The observed maximum cavity pressure near and away from the injection point was approximately 54 bar and 39 bar respectively. After the compression step, the curing step was carried out and then the laminate was demolded.

For rest of the laminates manufactured by HP-IRTM and HP-CRTM process at different resin flow rates only the resin injection step time varied accordingly with minor deviations in the cavity pressure values. These results will be presented directly during the conference. Also for the experiments conducted using vacuum, an additional time of 30 s was essential before the start of resin injection step to evacuate the mold cavity. Hence these results will also be presented directly during the conference.

6.2 Fiber volume content in the HP-RTM laminates

The fiber volume content in the manufactured HP-RTM laminates was measured by the ashing experiments.

Fig. 6. Average fiber volume content in HP-RTM laminates (V stands for vacuum)

For measurement of the fiber volume content samples were cut from the laminates from the sections near and away from the injection point. The section near the injection point resembles to the laminate area of 560 mm x 400 mm, of which, 560 mm is the mold width and 400 mm is the mold length with resin injection gate exactly in the middle of 400 mm mold length (laminate area near the

injection point extending 200 mm on either side of the resin injection gate). Rest of the laminate area is referred as section away from the injection point and this area is comparatively very close to the vacuum ports of the mold. In order to avoid any influences of the laminate thickness variations all the fiber volume content values were normalized to a laminate thickness of 1.7 mm.

During analysis no influence of resin flow rate was observed on the fiber volume content values of samples if these samples were compared for their fiber volume content values respectively in the sections near and away from the injection point. The average fiber volume content values (bar values) in figure 6 are derived by taking the average of fiber volume content values of the samples manufactured using 40 g/s, 60 g/s and 80 g/s resin flow rate. As can be seen for all the experimental series the fiber volume content in the section away from the injection point was always slightly higher than the fiber volume content in the section near the injection point. Further, no influence of use of vacuum was observed on the fiber volume content of the laminates.

6.3 Flexural properties

The flexural properties of all HP-IRTM experimental series conducted with and without vacuum are given in table 2.

Expt. Series	Resin injection rate [g/s]	Vacuum use	Flexural strength [MPa] ± standard deviation	Flexural strength improvement [%]	Flexural modulus [GPa] ± standard deviation	Flexural modulus improvement [%]
1	40	x	638 ± 81	Ref.	45 ± 4.4	Ref.
1	40	✓	734 ± 63	15% ↑	50 ± 4.9	11% ↑
2	60	x	694 ± 48	Ref.	48 ± 2.1	Ref.
2	60	✓	772 ± 31	11% ↑	54 ± 2.6	13% ↑
3	80	x	693 ± 53	Ref.	47 ± 3.1	Ref.
3	80	✓	746 ± 60	8% ↑	49 ± 4.3	4% ↑
HP-IRTM process w/o vacuum			675 ± 66	Ref.	47 ± 3.5	Ref.
HP-IRTM process with vacuum			751 ± 55	11% ↑	51 ± 4.6	9% ↑

Tab. 2. Flexural properties of HP-IRTM laminates (± values indicate standard deviation)

As can be seen in table 2, each experimental series conducted without use of vacuum is mentioned as a reference series. For understanding the effect of use of vacuum on the laminate quality, the flexural properties of laminates manufactured using vacuum are compared with the respective reference series

and the property improvement in percentage is mentioned accordingly. As can be seen from table 2, using vacuum led to higher average flexural properties of the HP-IRTM laminates irrespective of the used resin flow rate.

Fig. 7. Flexural properties of the HP-IRTM laminates manufactured with and without use of vacuum

In figure 7 flexural properties of individual samples from HP-IRTM laminates are presented. As can be seen, lower flexural properties can be observed if no vacuum is used and the flexural properties tend to be higher if vacuum is used. For all the HP-IRTM experimental series without vacuum average flexural strength of 675 MPa and average flexural modulus of 47 GPa was measured. If vacuum was used, the average flexural strength of 751 MPa (11 % higher) and average flexural modulus of 51 GPa (9 % higher) was measured.

Expt. Series	Resin injection rate [g/s]	Vacuum use	Flexural strength [MPa] ± standard deviation	Flexural strength improvement [%]	Flexural modulus [GPa] ± standard deviation	Flexural modulus improvement [%]
4	40	x	644 ± 44	Ref.	44 ± 2.7	Ref.
4	40	✓	704 ± 30	9% ↑	47 ± 3.8	7% ↑
5	60	x	652 ± 108	Ref.	46 ± 5.5	Ref.
5	60	✓	712 ± 46	9% ↑	49 ± 5	7% ↑
6	80	x	613 ± 51	Ref.	42 ± 4.4	Ref.
6	80	✓	735 ± 70	20% ↑	49 ± 6.3	17% ↑
HP-CRTM process w/ovacuum			636 ± 71	Ref.	44 ± 4.6	Ref.
HP-CRTM process with vacuum			717 ± 53	13% ↑	49 ± 5.1	11% ↑

Tab. 3. Flexural properties of HP-CRTM laminates (± values indicate standard deviation)

The flexural properties of all HP-CRTM experimental series conducted with and without vacuum are given in table 3. Similar to the HP-IRTM process, as can be seen, using vacuum higher average flexural properties of the HP-CRTM laminates irrespective of the used resin flow rate were measured.

Fig. 8. Flexural properties of the HP-CRTM laminates manufactured with and without use of vacuum

In figure 8 flexural properties of individual samples from HP-CRTM laminates are presented. For the HP-CRTM laminates as well higher flexural properties were measured if vacuum was used if compared to flexural properties of samples manufactured without use of vacuum. For all the HP-CRTM experimental series without vacuum average flexural strength of 636 MPa and average flexural modulus of 44 GPa was measured. If vacuum was used, the average flexural strength of 717 MPa (13 % higher) and average flexural modulus of 48.5 GPa (11 % higher) was measured. A similar effect of use of vacuum on the higher flexural properties was also reported by Khoun et al in another study conducted for HP-RTM process variants [10].

6.4 ILSS properties

The ILSS properties of all HP-IRTM experimental series conducted with and without vacuum are given in table 4.

Experimental series	Resin injection rate [g/s]	Vacuum application	ILSS [MPa] ± standard deviation	ILSS improvement [%]
1	40	x	61 ± 2.5	Ref.
1	40	✓	65 ± 1.1	7% ↑
2	60	x	63 ± 1.6	Ref.
2	60	✓	66 ± 1.1	5% ↑
3	80	x	62 ± 4.1	Ref.
3	80	✓	66 ± 2.8	6% ↑

Tab. 4. ILSS of HP-IRTM laminates

Fig. 9. ILSS properties of the HP-IRTM laminates

As can be seen, similar to the observations for flexural properties, using vacuum led to slightly higher average ILSS properties of the HP-IRTM laminates irrespective of the used resin flow rate. While taking into account the standard deviation, however, this increase in the ILSS is not significantly high. In figure 9 ILSS properties of individual samples from HP-IRTM laminates are presented. Figure 9 shows that lower deviation in the ILSS properties was obtained if vacuum was used for manufacturing of HP-IRTM laminates at all the resin flow rates. Especially at 80 g/s resin flow rate, if no vacuum was used, then a relatively higher deviation in the ILSS can be observed.

Experimental series	Resin injection rate [g/s]	Vacuum application	ILSS [MPa] ± standard deviation	ILSS improvement [%]
4	40	x	64 ± 3.8	Ref.
4	40	✓	66 ± 2.5	3% ↑
5	60	x	63 ± 3.2	Ref.
5	60	✓	64 ± 2.6	2% ↑
6	80	x	59 ± 6.8	Ref.
6	80	✓	67 ± 2.4	14% ↑

Tab. 5. ILSS of HP-CRTM laminates

Fig. 10. ILSS properties of the HP-CRTM laminates

The ILSS properties of the HP-CRTM laminates are given in table 5. In case of HP-CRTM process at 40 g/s and 60 g/s resin flow rate only a minimum increase in ILSS average value can be observed if vacuum was used which actually can be neglected while considering the standard deviation.

Similar to the HP-IRTM process, as seen in figure 10, in case of HP-CRTM process as well higher deviation in the ILSS was observed if now vacuum was used at 80 g/s resin flow rate.

7 Conclusion

In the current study the HP-RTM process variants were studied using a fast curing resin system with a curing time of 5 min. While considering the need for manufacturing large surface area components it is essential to inject the resin in as short time as

possible to be able to use fast curing resin systems for high-volume manufacturing of the automotive components. Hence HP-IRTM and HP-CRTM processes were studying at different resin flow rate varying from 40 g/s, 60 g/s to 80 g/s. In principle due to non-reduced permeability of the textile reinforcement and due to presence of small mold gap in the HP-CRTM process the resin injection step can be carried out without any pressure built-up in the mold cavity. In case of HP-IRTM process, however, during the resin injection step the cavity pressure increased continuously. The infiltration process in the HP-CRTM process is completed by applying the compression step, which otherwise in the HP-IRTM process is completed by cavity pressure built-up during the resin injection step.

The characterization of the laminates manufactured by HP-IRTM and HP-CRTM process however did not show any differences in the physical and basic mechanical properties if these properties were compared to each other at constant process configuration (e.g. constant flow rate and vacuum condition being not varied). In both the process variants, resin flow rate did not show any influence on the flexural properties. In general higher average flexural properties were measured in both the process variants if vacuum was used to evacuate the mold cavity before starting resin injection step. The average ILSS properties of the laminates manufactured by both the process variants showed higher deviation at 80 g/s resin flow rate and applying vacuum in both the processes helped to stabilize the ILSS properties.

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